

10 reasons why I moved my publications from SlideShare to Zenodo, and keep them on Wikimedia Commons

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Abstract ⁽¹⁾ : In this article the Wikimedia coordinator of the KB, the national library of the Netherlands, explains why he decided to migrate all KB's Wikimedia-related publications of the last 13 years from SlideShare to Zenodo, while retaining copies of them on Wikimedia Commons. After explaining the importance of Wikimedia Commons for sharing, reusing and preserving sustainable open knowledge, he examines the limitations of SlideShare, and to a lesser extent Wikimedia Commons, in meeting the evolving needs of modern digital content sharing, particularly within scientific and research communities. Zenodo, an EU-based repository, is presented as a superior alternative due to its support for a wide range of file formats, persistent identifiers (DOIs), large file hosting, adherence to FAIR principles, content licensing options, multi-level sustainability and machine interaction capabilities. The author discusses ten strengths and two downsides of Zenodo that meet his personal professional needs, providing concrete examples of how Zenodo improves the findability, visibility, reusability, durability, and scholarly integration of his work in comparison to SlideShare and Wikimedia Commons.

Keywords ⁽¹⁾ : Zenodo, Wikimedia Commons, SlideShare, FAIR principles, Open access, Creative Commons, Persistent identifiers, Data repositories, Digital preservation, Scientific publishing, Digital sustainability, EU-based hosting, Wikimedia community, KB national library of the Netherlands, Koninklijke Bibliotheek

Topics ⁽²⁾ : Challenges and drawbacks of using Zenodo compared to SlideShare; Wikimedia Commons as an archive for KB content; Limitations of SlideShare in scientific contexts; Advantages of Zenodo for research data management; Integration of research outputs with academic aggregators; Legal and jurisdictional considerations for data hosting; The importance of FAIR data principles; Enhancing content discoverability and reuse through Zenodo; Durability and long-term accessibility of digital content.

As the [Wikimedia coordinator](#) of the KB, the national library of the Netherlands, sharing knowledge is an integral and important part of my job. Not only live during events, but also for knowledge reference and sustainability purposes after the events have ended.

Wikimedia Commons

This is why I make all Wikimedia-related presentations, articles, reports, workshop materials, tutorials, videos and other publications available in the bilingual [KB Wikimedia presentations & publications archive](#) on Wikimedia Commons. I've been doing so for the last 13 years. This ensures all such KB content:

- can be easily found via search engines (Google loves Wiki),
- is available for reuse in the [700+ Wikimedia projects](#) and communities,
- can be reused freely by the entire world because open (Creative Commons) licensing is mandatory,
- can be used as linked open data, independent of language, because multilingual [Structured Data](#) has been added to many of these files,
- is stored in a durable way; this year, Wikimedia Commons is celebrating its 20th anniversary and future financing and governance look strong.

Archived presentations & publications, by year [\[edit \]](#)

2024 [\[edit \]](#)

<p>25 June 2024 - The presentation Wikification of KB's digital collections explains the added value of putting images, stories and metadata of digitised collection highlights of the KB into the Wikimedia infrastructure. By putting these into Wikidata (metadata), Wikimedia Commons (images) and Wikipedia (stories), dozens of new functionalities have been created that are not available on KB's own websites.</p>	<p>6 June 2024 - Introduction course about Wikipedia, Wikimedia, Wikimedia Commons and GLAM-Wiki for (new) KB staff.</p>	<p>1 February 2024 - Reuse of KB images and source references in Wikipedia (2023) - Short explanation (in Dutch) about the use of KB collection images in (all language versions of) Wikipedia in 2023 and the utilization of source references to KB services in Dutch Wikipedia in the same year.</p>	<p>24 January 2024 - Reuse indicators for KB images in Wikipedia and Wikimedia Commons, the 2023 update - Wikipedia is a very effective channel to globally improve the findability, visibility and reusability of images from the heritage collections of KB. This can be measured by three reuse indicators (KPIs). This article gives an update of the growth of these KPIs during 2023.</p>	<p>12 January 2024 - Where to find public domain images and how to upload them to Wikimedia Commons - Workshop during Dutch Public Domain day 2024</p>
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2023 [\[edit \]](#)

<p>6 December 2023 - Introduction about Wikibase in relation to medieval manuscripts. See also the textual summary on GitHub.</p>	<p>14 November 2023 - In depth: Wikidata & KB - An overview of how Wikidata is used by/in for the services of the KB, national library of the Netherlands. Also see the textual summary on GitHub.</p>	<p>7 November 2023 - Video: Setting up your own Wikibase reconciliation service (e.g. for OpenRefine) - Video tutorial on how to install a reconciliation service for your own Wikibase instance, how to connect it to OpenRefine and what settings in the Wikibase itself need to be checked to allow data from OpenRefine to be written to the Wikibase.</p>	<p>7 November 2023 - Setting up your own Wikibase reconciliation service (e.g. for OpenRefine) - How to install a reconciliation service for your own Wikibase instance, how to connect it to OpenRefine and what settings in the Wikibase itself need to be checked to allow data from OpenRefine to be written to the Wikibase.</p>	<p>2 November 2023 - Video: Wat doet een Wikimedia-coördinator in de Koninklijke Bibliotheek? - Video registration of this presentation explaining some of the specific tasks of the Wikimedia coordinator of the KB.</p>
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Screenshot of the KB Wikimedia presentations & publications archive on Wikimedia Commons, dd 16 August 2024.

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/GLAM_at_Koninklijke_Bibliotheek/Archive

SlideShare and new needs

In addition to Wikimedia Commons, I also used to upload [my outputs to SlideShare](#). When I started doing this 14 years ago, my publishing and sharing needs were relatively simple and naive, with visibility and findability being the main purposes. SlideShare met this need, as it is well-indexed by search engines, has a visual-first user experience, and can be embedded into LinkedIn and Twitter posts.

At that time I had no need for (or awareness of) more advanced functionalities, such as

- Sharing a wider variety of file formats, beyond the typical “presentation oriented” PDF and JPG, such as more “data oriented” formats like JSON, TSV, Markdown, Jupyter notebooks or zipped OpenRefine project files.
- Publishing constituent workshop materials under one unique and persistent identifier – i.e. making all slides, notes, guide for participants, CSV with data, Jupyter notebooks or OpenRefine files used for a typical (data)workshop accessible as a combined package via a single URL.
- Sharing large files, such as video recording of live presentations of 100s of MBs, or entire datasets of hundreds of hi-res images and their descriptive metadata files.
- Adhering to [FAIR principles](#).
- REST APIs to interact with the publications programmatically.
- OAI-PMH-connectivity for exchanging publications with other repositories.

Although Wikimedia and/or SlideShare can meet some of these needs, over the years I gradually found out that they were not really potent enough to meet my ever increasing publication needs for my work to be discoverable and reusable by as many people, institutions and machines as possible, now and in the future, in a durable way, with low risk of their URLs becoming 404s or not findable at all.

Furthermore, the KB is a scientific institution and thus part of the international science and research communities. So as an employee of such an institution, I felt a need to also make my publications more strongly integrated into these communities. Both Wikimedia Commons and SlideShare fail to meet this need, neither of them has a strong user base in academic publishing.

Finally, as a European user of SlideShare, without going into all (legal) details, I felt some stress about having my content hosted on servers located in the US and being under that jurisdiction. This stimulated me to look for EU-based hosting alternatives.

New publication strategy, including Zenodo

The new needs and insights I developed over these years slowly but surely urged me to change my approach to storing and sharing my content. As the KB has been a part of the Wikimedia community for many years, an important requirement was to keep all Wikimedia-related KB output available through Wikimedia Commons. However, for the KB content hosted on SlideShare, I needed to find a better place, closer to home, on EU-based servers, with a service meeting as many of my demands as possible.

After doing some (non-exhaustive) comparison, using the [Generalist Repository Comparison Chart](#) among others, I picked Zenodo as the best match for my needs. In summary, *Zenodo is a general-purpose EU-hosted data repository built on open-source software that accepts all forms of research output, including presentations, research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital artefact. For each submission, a persistent [digital object identifier \(DOI\)](#) is minted, which makes the stored items easily citable.*

My choice for Zenodo was also influenced by my wish to comply with KB's earlier choice of Zenodo as its preferred repository; employee-generated publications have been stored in its [KB community](#) since 2017.

Gradually I started moving my Wikimedia-related content from SlideShare to Zenodo. Along the way I also improved and harmonized the descriptions and other metadata associated with the files. Of course I made sure to submit all my content to the KB community as well. I completed this task in the summer of 2024, making all these [presentations, articles, reports, tutorials, videos and other publications](#) now accessible from Zenodo.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo profile of Olaf Janssen, affiliated with the Koninklijke Bibliotheek. The profile includes a 'New upload' button and navigation tabs for 'Uploads', 'Communities', and 'Requests'. The 'Uploads' tab is active, displaying a search bar and a 'Sort by' dropdown set to 'Most viewed'. Two publications are listed:

- November 3, 2022 (v1)**: A 'Publication' that is 'Open'. The title is 'Nepartikelen op Wikipedia, 03-11-2022'. The description states: 'Als meest gebruikte naslagwerk ter wereld heeft Wikipedia een belangrijke rol om mensen van betrouwbare informatie te voorzien. Juist vanwege die functie en het grote bereik is Wikipedia een aantrekkelijke plek om onjuiste informatie de wereld in te helpen. Het is daarom van groot belang dat nepartikelen snel herkend en verwijderd worden. In dit...'. It is part of 'KB, national library of the Netherlands' and was uploaded on November 3, 2022. It has 133 views and 94 downloads.
- July 3, 2018 (v1)**: A 'Journal article' that is 'Open'. The title is 'Open data in de Koninklijke Bibliotheek - Od Magazine, jrg. 72, nr. 5, juni 2018'. The description states: 'Als nationale bibliotheek verzamelt de Koninklijke Bibliotheek (KB) alle publicaties van en over Nederland, van handschriften uit de Middeleeuwen tot de krant van gisteren. Het is onze taak om dit erfgoed zo breed en open mogelijk beschikbaar, vindbaar en herbruikbaar te maken. Dit artikel geeft in vogelvlucht weer hoe de KB dit aanpakt. Dit arti...'. It is part of 'KB, national library of the Netherlands' and was uploaded on March 30, 2023. It has 120 views and 40 downloads.

Screenshot of Olaf Janssen's Zenodo account, dd 16 August 2024, now including all his Wikimedia-related publications that were previously hosted on SlideShare.

<https://zenodo.org/search?q=creators.orcid:%220000-0002-9058-9941%22> with 0000-0002-9058-9941 being the ORCID id of the author.

My Top 10 Zenodo features

Let us now look at the ten Zenodo features that are most relevant for meeting my personal needs and wishes, in comparison to SlideShare and Wikimedia Commons. I have no ambition to discuss the complete feature set Zenodo has to offer; if you are interested in that, you can

check Zenodo's detailed public [About](#), [Principles](#), [General Policies](#), [Privacy Policy](#) and [Infrastructure](#) documents.

The 10 advantages of Zenodo most important to me are :

- 1) **Sharing a wide variety of file formats**, beyond the typical "presentation-oriented" PDF and JPG, such as more "data-oriented" formats like JSON, TSV, Markdown, Jupyter notebooks, or zipped files. Zenodo is very flexible, as it [supports uploading files in any format](#). Wikimedia Commons has a [smaller set](#) of supported formats and SlideShare only allows [PowerPoint, PDF and Word](#) files.

Example: The [Workshop OpenRefine en Wikimedia Commons \(19-11-2022\)](#) hosts files in tar.gz, pdf, xlsx, txt and json formats.

Name	Size
Dataset-WorkshopOpenRefine-WikiconNL19112022-xlsx.openrefine.tar.gz md5:2dd5b4dd9e6227d6d29ac892d9010637	51.3 kB
Dataset_WorkshopOpenRefine_WikiconNL19112022.xlsx md5:c492a86dea86dfd0b6774d2e4def8fc1	27.8 kB
github_URL.txt md5:cd94946f9aa41be7774f88bad4dd9944	69 Bytes
schemaHavengezichtenGvN.json md5:58b989ce6fb6c6df1faae651ec3191a1	3.1 kB
wiki-urls.txt md5:e7673345a9e5eabd46dc08b2b339154f	1.0 kB
Workshop OpenRefine en Wikimedia Commons - Olaf Janssen - WikiconNL_19112022.pdf md5:9b77eb14d6a67ff9261b85347b475df6	8.2 MB

Screenshot of the files used in 'Workshop OpenRefine en Wikimedia Commons', hosting tar.gz, pdf, xlsx, txt and json formats - <https://zenodo.org/records/7665231>

- 2) **Publishing constituent workshop materials** under one unique and persistent identifier. When running a typical data-oriented workshop, it is very convenient - both for the participants and for post-workshop archiving - to publish all materials (slides, notes, guide for participants, csv with data, Jupyter notebooks, Openrefine project files, etc.) as a combined package in a single location under a single durable URI or DOI. This is a real added value of Zenodo, as both SlideShare and Wikimedia Commons allow only one file per upload.

Example: This [OpenRefine Introduction Workshop \(2023\)](#) packages six files (pdf, xlsx, txt, and md) into a single upload.

- 3) **Sharing large files**, with personal use cases including video recording of live presentations of hundreds of MBs, or datasets containing large numbers of hi-res

images and their descriptive metadata files (1+ GB). SlideShare has a [300MB limit](#) and Wikimedia Commons allows 100MB by default, or up to 5GB when using [chunked uploading](#). Zenodo has a default [50GB file size limit](#) for each publication, which is more than enough for my needs.

Example: Hosting the 397 MB video [Wikidata in de praktijk bij de Koninklijke Bibliotheek, masterclass Wikidata \(28-05-2021\)](#) is well within Zenodo's file size limits.

- 4) **Restricting access to files and saving drafts** are [features in Zenodo](#) that allow editors to work on (drafts of) records in a closed-off environment before releasing them to the public. Wikimedia Commons does not offer this, as every file there is publicly accessible, and under version control right from the start, making it unsuitable for drafting temporary or permanent non-open publications.

Example: I'm currently preparing a [Wikidata introduction workshop for Maastricht University](#) and already uploaded some draft materials for this event to Zenodo. When the preparations are finished, I will openly share the files with the participants via <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11224632>

Screenshot of restricted draft materials for an upcoming Wikidata workshop on 15 October 2024. Files will be accessible via <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11224632> after that date.

5) **Wider licensing options** compared to Wikimedia Commons and SlideShare. By default, I publish and share my content under open licenses, either CC-BY, CC-BY-SA or even CC0. This makes my publications [suitable for Wikimedia Commons](#) as well as [for SlideShare](#). However, in some cases, I would like to have a bit more control over derivative or commercial reuses of my works, for which CC-BY-ND and/or CC-BY-NC licensing are appropriate instruments. This makes these kinds of works unsuitable for sharing on Wikimedia Commons, but SlideShare would still be an option, as these more restrictive licenses are allowed there.

Zenodo accommodates all of the above scenarios, as it allows for both very open (CC0) and less open (CC-BY-NC/ND) licenses, as well as over [600 alternative options](#), both for presentation-oriented and data-oriented publication. So in the vast majority of cases, there is always a suitable license to choose from.

The only exception is the 'All rights reserved' case. It is allowed by SlideShare, but not on either open-oriented platform. However, I can use this limitation of Zenodo and Commons as a stimulant to always create publications that are suitable for sharing (be it under a CC-BY-ND/NC clause) and reuse when possible (without the ND clause).

Version: 3.25.0 2024-08-19

Note: You can sort by each column by clicking on the column header. By default, the table sorts by the Identifier column.

Full name	Identifier
BSD Zero Clause License	0BSD
3D Slicer License v1.0	3D-Slicer-1.0
Attribution Assurance License	AAL
Abstyles License	Abstyles
AdaCore Doc License	AdaCore-doc
Adobe Systems Incorporated Source Code License Agreement	Adobe-2006
Adobe Display PostScript License	Adobe-Display-PostScript
Adobe Glyph List License	Adobe-Glyph
Adobe Utopia Font License	Adobe-Utopia
Amazon Digital Services License	ADSL
Academic Free License v1.1	AFL-1.1
Academic Free License v1.2	AFL-1.2
Academic Free License v2.0	AFL-2.0
Academic Free License v2.1	AFL-2.1
Academic Free License v3.0	AFL-3.0
Afmparse License	Afmparse
Affero General Public License v1.0 only	AGPL-1.0-only
Affero General Public License v1.0 or later	AGPL-1.0-or-later
GNU Affero General Public License v3.0 only	AGPL-3.0-only
GNU Affero General Public License v3.0 or later	AGPL-3.0-or-later
Aladdin Free Public License	Aladdin
AMD newlib License	AMD-newlib
AMD's plpa_map.c License	AMDPLPA
Apple MIT License	AML

List of over 600 licensing options used by Zenodo, from <https://spdx.org/licenses>

- 6) **Adhering to FAIR principles.** Zenodo's [Principles page](#) explains in detail how the repository adheres to the [FAIR principles](#) of being Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.

This makes Zenodo more FAIR-compliant than Wikimedia Commons. Although all uploads get their own unique persistent M-identifiers (so-called Concept URIs, such as <https://commons.wikimedia.org/entity/M144836996>), these play a less manifest and significant role than their DOI equivalents in Zenodo. Multilingual findability is limited by the English-oriented [category names](#) used to group files. On the positive side, metadata of each upload is indexed and searchable via the Wikimedia Commons search engine immediately after publishing. Additionally, all files and their metadata can be requested for free via a set of [REST-APIs](#) without the need for a user account. However, interoperability is non-ideal as Commons uses metadata standards that are not necessarily compatible with ontologies in the cultural heritage and humanities domains. Also Commons does not offer support for standards like IIRF, although [some attempts](#) have been made in the past. All Commons files can be reused because open (Creative Commons) licenses are mandatory. Finally, thanks to the [Structured Data on Commons](#) effort, Wikidata has been integrated into Commons. This means all [FAIR strongpoints of Wikidata](#) (*"Wikidata fulfills the most complete degree of FAIRness"*) are now exposed to Commons as well.

As for SlideShare, it is a purely presentation-oriented and visual-first environment, with no explicit attention to being FAIR. It does for instance not use unique and persistent identifiers for its uploads, nor does it offer rich and explicit metadata for them. Publications are not linked to open, external vocabularies, and you will need to have an account to be able to download content and their (very basic) metadata.

- 7) **Durability for files, governance and funding:** Zenodo was launched in May 2013 and is hosted as an embedded [service of CERN](#), which has existed for 70 years and currently has programs defined for the next 20+ years. Files are stored with [longevity](#) as a primary focus.

[Additional checks and balances](#) with respect to the infrastructure, servers, storage, security, governance, financing, and legal status all contribute to future-proofing the repository.

This is at least on par with the sustainability of Wikimedia Commons, which has been in operation for 20 years now. It is part of the [Wikimedia Foundation](#) portfolio, and as such, is funded and governed by the [overall policies](#) of the Wikimedia movement, with durability, transparency, openness and reliability at its core. Long-term funding of its projects is secured by the [Wikimedia Endowment](#), aiming to support Wikimedia projects in perpetuity.

As for SlideShare, it is operated by [Scribd](#), a U.S.-based privately owned company funded by [venture capital](#). Obviously, this is not an ideal situation to ensure long term

accessibility of content hosted on SlideShare. This was another reason to migrate my content from there onto Zenodo.

- 8) **Contributing to international research:** The KB is a scientific organization and, as such, part of the international science and research communities. As an employee of such an institution, Zenodo allows me to automatically integrate my publications into scholarly aggregators, such as [ORCID](#), [DataCite](#), [OpenAIRE](#), [BASE](#) or [FID Benelux](#), making them more visible for study and research purposes, without any extra effort on my part.

Both Wikimedia Commons and SlideShare are not yet well integrated into academic workflows and don't have strong user bases in the scholarly community. By exposing my Wikimedia-related publications to this target group, I hope to raise more awareness of the benefits that Wikimedia can bring to their fields of work.

The screenshot displays the OpenAIRE EXPLORE interface. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation tabs for 'RESEARCH PRODUCTS (47)', 'PROJECTS (0)', 'DATA SOURCES (0)', and 'ORGANIZATIONS (0)'. A sidebar on the left contains filters for 'Access' (Open Access, Closed Access, Restricted, Open Source, Embargo), 'Type' (Publications, Research Data, Research Software, Other Research Products), 'Year range' (1800 - 2034), and 'Country' (BE (1)). The main content area shows 47 research products for user 0000-0002-9058-9941. Three publications are visible:

- Wikification of KB's digital collections - KB summerschool, 25 June 2024**
Publication » Presentation • 2024 • English • Publisher: Zenodo
Authors: Janssen, Olaf;
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12188301, 10.5281/zenodo.12188300
This 45 minutes presentation explains the added value of putting images, stories and metadata of digitised collection highlights of the KB, national library of the Netherlands, into the Wikimedia infrastructure. By putting our collection highlights into Wikidata...
- Hergebruik KB-beelden en -bronverwijzingen in Wikipedia (2023) - Afdelingsoverleg M&E, Koninklijke Bibliotheek, 1 februari 2024**
Publication » Other literature type, Presentation • 2024 • Dutch; Flemish • Publisher: Zenodo
Authors: Janssen, Olaf;
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10602579, 10.5281/zenodo.10602580
English: This presentation for colleagues from the KB, national library of the Netherlands, answers two questions: 1) Where and how often have KB collection images been used in (all language versions of) Wikipedia in 2023? This is based on the previously...
- Reuse indicators for KB images in Wikipedia and Wikimedia Commons, the 2023 update**
Publication » Report • 2024 • English • Publisher: Zenodo
Authors: Janssen, Olaf;
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10561248, 10.5281/zenodo.10561249
Key Takeaway The web page discusses the reuse indicators for KB (national library of the Netherlands) images, Wikimedia Commons, specifically focusing on the 2023 update. It highlights the effectiveness of Wikipedia in making KB...

Screenshot of the author's publications as listed in OpenAIRE on 22 August 2024. All records were automatically imported from Zenodo, based on the [ORCID of the author](#). ([Source of image](#)).

- 9) **Hosted on EU-based servers:** Zenodo is powered by the [CERN Data Centre](#), physically located in France. This means it is subject to CERN's legal status as an intergovernmental organization with immunity from the jurisdictions of the nation courts of the EU Member States ([source](#)). This effectively safeguards Zenodo from

being taken down due to legal procedures initiated by hostile agents.

Although Wikimedia Commons [runs in data centers](#) partly located in the EU (Amsterdam and Marseille), the platform legally falls under U.S. jurisdiction, as its operator, the Wikimedia Foundation, is a nonprofit public charity under U.S. law.

10) **The REST API and OAI-PMH interface** allow for programmatic interactions with my publications. In accordance with the [Collections as Data](#) initiative, these APIs allow me to expose my “Publications as Data”, supporting computationally-driven sharing, research and teaching.

Zenodo’s [REST API](#) allows publication metadata to be requested directly in JSON format ([example](#)) that can be processed further via Python and other languages. For instance, with only a few lines of code, you can request all my publications [as an Excel file](#). Via Zenodo’s [OAI-PMH interface](#), all publications in the [KB community](#) can be requested in [various metadata formats](#), including the library-oriented [OAI DC](#) or [MARC21](#) schemes. This protocol is used by the scholarly aggregators listed in point 8) to ingest KB publications into their repositories.

As for Wikimedia Commons, the MediaWiki software used by this platform offers a set of rich and free [REST-APIs](#) allowing for a wide range of machine interactions with my publications. Furthermore, thanks to the [Structured Data on Commons](#) effort, all my publications will soon be available as Linked Open Data that can be queried via the [Wikimedia Commons SPARQL service](#). Unfortunately, Commons does not offer an OAI-PMH interface.

SlideShare [used to have](#) a REST API, but it seems to have been [inactive for several years](#) now.

Downsides of Zenodo

Given all these positive features, you might think there are no downsides to sharing your presentations, articles, tutorials, and other publications via Zenodo. Well, of course there are! Coming from SlideShare and Wikimedia Commons backgrounds, two drawbacks of Zenodo I’ve personally encountered into are:

- 1) **Zenodo is not well known among regular web users**, as it is not part of the mainstream internet. Compared to SlideShare, still [ranked in the top 600](#) of most visited websites worldwide, Zenodo is [far more long-tail](#) and niche (ranked 55K+). This lowers the chances for my publications to be spontaneously discovered via search engines or social media by general web users. This disadvantage is however mitigated by my publications also being available on Wikimedia Commons, which has a much better exposure to search engines compared to Zenodo. This makes my presentations findable outside the scientific communication and publication channels.

Furthermore, most of my content is not aimed at the general public, but rather at professional, specialized target groups, including library and digital heritage professionals, data-oriented scholars (digital humanities), and the Wikimedia communities. These types of users will probably be more likely to visit Zenodo (and Wikimedia Commons) than SlideShare when looking for this sort of content.

2) **Zenodo does not offer a visual-first user experience.** This is especially apparent when looking at how search results for the query “koninklijke bibliotheek” are displayed on SlideShare versus Zenodo. The [default gallery view](#) used by SlideShare is visually more appealing than the [text-oriented display](#) of Zenodo’s results.

For the publications themselves, a [typical SlideShare page](#) offers a much stronger visual-first experience than a [typical Zenodo record](#) page, which contains much more manifest textual (metadata) elements.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo search results page for the query "koninklijke bibliotheek". The page features a blue header with the Zenodo logo and a hamburger menu icon. Below the header, there is a search bar showing "371 result(s) found" and a "Sort by" dropdown menu set to "Best match". The search results are displayed in a list format, with each result card containing a date, a title, authors, a description, and a "Part of" link to the national library of the Netherlands. The first result is titled "6 maanden Wikipedian-in-Residence KB en NA, Voortgang & vooruitblik, 01-04-2014" by Janssen, Olaf; Kranen, Hay; de Haan, Tim. The second result is titled "Open data Koninklijke Bibliotheek, hergebruik op Wikipedia, Commons en Wikisource - KB, 08-06-2013" by Janssen, Olaf. The third result is titled "Reuse indicators for KB images in Wikipedia and Wikimedia Commons, the 2023 update" by Janssen, Olaf. Each result card also includes a "Presentation" or "Report" label, an "Open" button, and view/download statistics.

For the query “koninklijke bibliotheek” the text-oriented [search results on Zenodo](#) do not offer the same visual-first user experience as the [same query on SlideShare](#).

Of course, these differences are hardly surprising because Zenodo was built as a scientific data-focused service, giving metadata the same (or even higher) priority as the object. But for users coming from the visual-first background of SlideShare, where most textual metadata is rather hidden, the differences are striking.

Fortunately, using its REST API and some Python code, it would be very feasible to generate a thumbnail gallery view for all my publications in Zenodo, mimicking the [KB Wikimedia presentations & publications archive](#) discussed at the start of this article.

Summary and conclusion ⁽¹⁾

In this article, I describe my journey in transitioning from SlideShare to Zenodo for hosting and sharing my professional Wikimedia-related content, while continuing to maintain KB's presence on Wikimedia Commons. As my publishing requirements evolved over time, the need for a more robust, versatile, and research-oriented platform became clear. While SlideShare initially met my basic needs for visibility and discoverability, its limitations—such as a narrow selection of file formats, lack of advanced metadata support, and concerns about long-term accessibility—prompted me to look for a better alternative.

Zenodo emerged as the optimal choice due to its EU-based hosting, support for a wide range of file types, and strong alignment with the FAIR principles of data management. The platform's ability to mint DOIs, manage large files, and integrate with academic repositories, along with its multi-level sustainability and machine interaction capabilities, significantly enhances the discoverability and reuse of my work within the international research community. Despite some drawbacks, such as its less visual-first user experience compared to SlideShare, Zenodo's strengths in durability, flexibility, and scholarly integration far outweigh these concerns.

In conclusion, Zenodo, in conjunction with Wikimedia Commons, provides a powerful and sustainable solution for managing and disseminating my professional outputs. By utilizing both platforms synergistically, I can ensure that my work remains accessible, reusable, and impactful for a diverse range of audiences, from general web users to specialized academic communities.

Nederlandstalige samenvatting ⁽¹⁾

In dit artikel legt de Wikimedia-coördinator van de KB, de nationale bibliotheek van Nederland, uit waarom hij heeft besloten om alle Wikimedia-gerelateerde publicaties van de KB van de afgelopen 13 jaar van SlideShare naar Zenodo te verhuizen, en tevens versies hiervan via Wikimedia Commons te ontsluiten.

Na het uitleggen van het belang van Wikimedia Commons voor het delen, hergebruiken en behouden van duurzame open kennis, onderzoekt hij in hoeverre SlideShare, en in mindere

mate Wikimedia Commons voldoen aan de eisen die digitale kennisdeling vandaag de dag stelt, met name binnen de context van wetenschap en onderzoek.

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De auteur bespreekt tien sterke punten en twee nadelen van Zenodo waar hij binnen zijn eigen werkzaamheden voor de KB tegenaan liep, en geeft concrete voorbeelden van hoe Zenodo de vindbaarheid, zichtbaarheid, herbruikbaarheid, duurzaamheid en wetenschappelijke integratie van zijn publicaties verbetert, vergeleken met SlideShare en Wikimedia Commons.

About the author

Olaf Janssen is the [Wikimedia coordinator](#) of the KB, the national library of the Netherlands. He contributes to [Wikipedia](#), [Wikimedia Commons](#) and [Wikidata](#) as [User:OlafJanssen](#)

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